

TRENDS AND FEATURES OF LIGHT INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN: ACHIEVEMENTS, PROBLEMS, AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract. *This article examines the development processes of light industry in the Republic of Karakalpakstan during the years of independence. Given that the nature, degree of influence, and nature of competitive factors in light industry differ significantly from other sectors, and its market activities exert a comprehensive influence on efficiency indicators, researching the competitiveness factors of economic entities operating in this field is particularly relevant. In this regard, forming the scientific and methodological foundations for their systematization, as well as analyzing employment issues in the industry, is of great importance. These aspects determine the scientific and practical significance of the chosen topic at the current stage.*

Keywords: *industrial sector, textile and garment industry, production cooperation, added value.*

INTRODUCTION

The textile industry of Uzbekistan is one of the most dynamically developing sectors of the national economy. It occupies a leading position in attracting foreign investment, creating new production enterprises, ensuring public employment and creating new jobs, and increasing the country's export potential. At the same time, the textile industry is one of the strategically priority areas for the development of the republic's economy, playing an important role in ensuring its sustainable growth and increasing competitiveness in the global market.

Relevance of the topic. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, light industry is one of the most developed sectors of the industrial complex. It accounts for about 33–35% of the annual industrial production volume and about 33.5% of the total number of people employed in industry.

In recent years, the light industry sector has undergone significant changes: reconstruction has been carried out, modern technological equipment has been introduced, and the geography of production capacity placement has been significantly transformed.

The historical dynamics of the industry's development indicate its steady growth. Thus, between 1961 and 1990, the value of fixed production assets in the light industry increased 3.7 times, which contributed to a 1.7-fold increase in production volumes.

At the current stage, the cotton ginning industry forms the basis of the republic's light industry, which is driven by the intensive development of cotton growing. Along with this, spinning and weaving enterprises, garment factories, and the production of knitwear products are operating [1].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Research shows that starting from the 1960s, the cotton ginning industry was actively formed in Karakalpakstan, which became the basis for the subsequent development of light industry. A significant factor in this process was the construction of the Charzhou–Kungrad

railway line, which ensured the transport accessibility of the region and opened opportunities for the supply of machinery and equipment from other regions of Central Asia and foreign countries. This contributed to the formation of a technical base and the rational territorial placement of industry enterprises [2].

The textile industry of Karakalpakstan is among the relatively new sectors. Initially, the republic established cotton-spinning enterprises in the cities of Khojeyli, Mangit, and Beruniy, as well as a production association for the production of cotton fabrics in Turtkul. During the years of independence, a significant impetus was given to the development of the industry: in May 1993, the "Kateks" textile enterprise was commissioned with the assistance of the Turkish company "Yazex." In its first year of operation, the enterprise produced 801,000 units of products worth 2 million 448 thousand soums.

By the mid-1990s, a steady increase in production capacity was observed. Thus, the Nukus "Kateks" Joint-Stock Company achieved a production level of 54 million 624 thousand soums, ensuring the production of 162 tons of cotton yarn and 1 million 883 thousand units of knitwear. During the same period, the "Eltex" joint-stock company in the Ellikkala district produced products worth 239,170,000 soums, producing 717 tons of cotton yarn and 1,932,000 square meters of cotton fabrics.

Significant contributions to the development of the industry were also made by enterprises in Turtkul, Beruniy, Mangit, and Khojeyli, where the total annual production volume reached 499.1 million soums, the output of cotton yarn reached 4.5 thousand tons, and knitted products exceeded 22 million square meters. Overall, the production volume of the republic's textile enterprises that began operations in the first years of independence amounted to 793 million soums.

According to statistical data, by 2009, the light industry sectors of Karakalpakstan produced 476 thousand square meters of cotton fabrics, 149 thousand tons of cotton fiber, and the total volume of finished products amounted to 119 billion soums. It is projected that when enterprises reach full production capacity, production volumes may increase by 1.8–2.5 times, indicating a high potential for the further development of the industry [3].

Light industry enterprises began exporting products in 1994. Between 1994 and 2015, the volume of product exports increased nearly tenfold. Today, the industry produces a wide range of export products (from cotton yarn to garments and knitwear). Enterprises of Uzbekengilsanoat continue to expand their presence in foreign countries. As confirmation of this, one can cite the fact that in 2015, the industry's export indicators exceeded 1 billion dollars, and the number of exporting enterprises reached 260. Their export structure includes new types of textile products: bamboo, modal, and blended yarn, jacquard and ring fabrics, as well as new types and models of finished garments and knitwear, distinguished by their original design and elegance. By the end of 2015, the share of high-value-added products in the export structure was 32.2% [1].

Within the framework of industrial potential development programs in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, new light industry enterprises were commissioned, including "Amudaryo Textile" in the Amudarya district, "Elit Star Textile" in the Khojeyli district, and "Global Textile" in the Ellikkala district. These enterprises have become an important element in modernizing the regional industrial structure and expanding the industry's processing capacities.

In accordance with the state programs for socio-economic development and industrial modernization for 2015–2019, the phased reconstruction of four existing enterprises that previously operated on the basis of cotton ginning plants and the construction of four new light

industry enterprises were envisaged. The implementation of these activities was carried out by attracting investments in the amount of 79.6 million US dollars, which reflects the intensification of industrial modernization processes and the growth of the investment attractiveness of the industry[6].

During the visits of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Republic of Karakalpakstan in January and December 2017, a project was proposed to create a large textile enterprise in the Kanlykul district. Over the past period, 10 hectares of land have been allocated for the enterprise, and construction work has begun. The construction of the enterprise was carried out by Kanteks Invest LLC, which has experience in the production of light industry products. As a result, a modern textile factory was built in an open area. Currently, work is underway to deliver and install the latest models of textile equipment from Germany, Switzerland, Turkey, and India. The enterprise, with a project cost of 38.7 million US dollars, is scheduled to be commissioned in the first quarter of next year. At the initial stage, it will produce 11 thousand tons of high-quality yarn per year. At the next stage, which will be launched in 2020, the production of textile materials will be established, and at the third stage, which will be implemented in 2021, the production of dyes and ready-made clothing will be established. Once the enterprise reaches full capacity, it will be possible to export products worth over 25 million US dollars per year. The head of state inspected the enterprise's production building, textile equipment, and spoke with the founders. To date, the factory, which will provide jobs for about 650 people, is selecting employees who are undergoing training at the training center established here, as well as improving their knowledge and qualifications at enterprises in other regions.

This is evidenced by the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2016, "On the Program of Measures for the Further Development of the Textile and Garment-Knitwear Industry for 2017–2019." This far-sighted resolution approved the "List of investment projects for the production of export-oriented textile and garment-knitted products with high added value based on the processing of cotton fiber and raw silk for 2016–2019," which included a project to organize the production of yarn and denim materials for the "Ellikkala Denim" joint venture. Most importantly, according to the resolution, it is determined that investment projects can be financed by commercial banks by entering the authorized capital, in particular, through foreign investment companies. In accordance with this, within the framework of the project to produce 4,000 tons of yarn and 10 million square meters of denim material per year, implemented by the "BOCTON MEGA TEKSTIL" Limited Liability Company established on the basis of "Ellikkala Denim" LLC, import contracts have been concluded to date with the Japanese firm MURATA MACHINERY, LTD for 792,000 euros, the Belgian PICANOL for 1,530,000 euros, the German TRUTZSCHLER for 1,380,940 euros, and the Chinese JINGWEI for 3,104,810 US dollars to purchase modern technological equipment and inventory of the latest models. Credit funds have been allocated by the National Bank, the necessary equipment and machines have been delivered, and installation work has begun. Additionally, construction and installation work worth 1.5 billion soums was carried out in the buildings with high quality.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

As a result of the special attention paid by our President to the Muynak district, many manufacturing enterprises are being launched and put into operation. The new enterprise, the construction of which began in February 2019, employed 350 women. On July 22, 2019, the garment factory of the "Muynak Textile" Limited Liability Company was commissioned. 320

modern sewing machines manufactured in the People's Republic of China and Turkey were installed here.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the creation of new industrial sectors in Karakalpakstan based on local raw material resources will, firstly, create conditions for improving the lives of the population, and secondly, solve the tasks of increasing the efficiency of economic sectors through the formation of production complexes.

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